

Helio2050 White Paper

The Science of Team Science and Inclusivity in Heliophysics

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Key Points:

- 1. The transdisciplinary aspect of Heliophysics requires solutions that address the cultural as well as the technical challenges**
- 2. We describe a new sensibility guided by *antidisciplinary* to overcome the cultural challenge**
- 3. Antidisciplinary means increased plurality of thought and transdisciplinary connections. It does *not* mean ‘against’ disciplines and other terms that could be used are polydisciplinary and omnidisciplinary**
- 4. The Science of "Team Science" (STS) is a proven approach that prioritizes Outcome-Based team formation. STS is inherently diverse, inclusive, and provides a powerful path to moving beyond traditional connections and *status quo*.**

The most fruitful areas for the growth of the sciences were those which had been neglected as a no-man's land between the various established fields. – Norbert Weiner

1 Introduction

Heliophysics is inherently transdisciplinary. It demands an understanding of disciplines as disparate as solar physics, plasma dynamics, geophysics, Earth science, atmospheric chemistry, radio science, electrical engineering, and data science. The user community provides an even more diverse group including power grids, aviation, and even tourism. In fact, the challenge to integrate the requisite disciplines, their individual jargon and nomenclature as well as their different cultures has precluded comprehensive modeling and research of Heliophysics science.

The challenge is as much cultural as it is technical. The approach that the sciences and engineering have traditionally followed is to focus on increasingly smaller groups and disciplines, so called ‘hyper-specialization.’ The reductionist approach has produced a sensibility of siloing, where communities have more similarity between mental models, less diversity, and fewer trans-domain connections. We believe that Heliophysics must address and counter each in the coming decades.

The purpose of this brief white paper is identify the cultural challenge, to suggest a new sensibility that responds to it, and to provide recommendations as a guide for our field in this open

and ongoing conversation. We encourage further consideration and community discussion around these ideas in the future.

We believe that the path lies in an embrace of *radical* collaboration, new scales of interaction, and the corresponding changes (in thinking, in community structure, and in support) that must accompany it. We refer to the approach as ‘*antidisciplinary*’ and the sensibility as ‘*flourishing-bringing*.’ Antidisciplinary is anything that does not fit comfortably or completely within traditional academic disciplines—a field of study with its own particular words, frameworks, and methods.

Antidisciplinary grows from the concept of sharing valuable information from across disciplines to catalyze any single discipline. Thus, antidisciplinary is in many ways synonymous with ideas that promote wider sharing and openness, ideas that perhaps enjoy wider celebration in the arts and design communities. Antidisciplinary is about building the standards that promote interoperability, between systems, individuals, and disciplines. But it is more than simply defining the standard. That step is a necessary but not sufficient condition. Antidisciplinary requires that one build on the new foundation for communication and interaction to embrace research that does not fall into one discipline. It requires *creation* and *innovation* – sharing ideas, combining, rearranging, amalgamating, in the service of producing the needed new.

2 Team Science, Diversity and Inclusion, and Breakthrough Potential

The National Research Council produced a report in 2015 titled “Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science” [1] where it outlined strategies to dramatically improve the potential of breakthrough research by developing truly diverse, balanced teams. The report authors included behavioral scientists and cognitive scientists as well as research physicists and informatics experts, who were able to identify strategies regarding the formation and function of teams that focus on collective capabilities and integrated strength.

The report discusses the way “traditional relationships” (more commonly called the “old boys network”) tend to solidify into teams that may be effective in the short term (because of their familiarity and trust) but are unable to adapt to long-term goals and address truly innovative challenges. It covers the importance of professional development, mentoring, and transition planning. It also anticipated our increasing dependence on virtual collaboration, with a 26-page chapter on how planning for geographically distributed participation can allow a team to attract exactly the talent base needed for success.

The report makes it clear that inclusivity does not happen on its own. It requires intention: a commitment to identifying areas for potential growth, a focus on a team’s potential weaknesses, and a willingness to “lean in” to new relationships that may initially be uncomfortable, but will pave the way to powerful long-term partnerships. Above all, it requires courage. There is a belief shared by many that if senior scientists spend more time mentoring and “encouraging” early-career, underrepresented, and minority scientists, the field will become more diverse and inclusive. But studies and surveys have consistently shown that minorities and people of color feel actively *discouraged* by culture and climate. The opposite of discouragement is not encouragement, it is *removal of the factors and barriers that create an unsafe and unwelcoming environment.* “Encouragement-based” strategies fail because 1) The people doing the encouraging tend to mentor those they feel most comfortable with, who help support their career, and whom typically look like them which 2) thereby reinforces the *status quo* and effectively reduces access for minorities and

Figure 1: Built into the DNA of science are the different types of research often categorized by their motivations. In order for science to progress all are necessary, but there is a clear need for knowledge transfer and cross pollination between them, which is can be covered through the adoption of antidisciplinary research

underrepresented populations. There is no aspect of the “Encouragement model” that enables and supports a more diverse workforce as the mentors remain the gatekeepers. Team Science boldly challenges the protégé-based hereditary power structures, and lays out a framework for flexible team formation that is able to embrace and adapt to ambitious new objectives.

3 Recommendations: The Path to Antidisciplinary Breakthroughs

How do we move toward this approach and sensibility?

1. Create review boards to identify the gaps in existing approaches to disciplinary integration
2. Make “Team Science” and balanced team formation an important evaluation criteria in proposals and educate reviewers on the importance of Team Science in eliminating status-quo-enabling networks thus increasing the scientific breakthrough potential of proposals
3. Create new programs that target systems science Heliophysics research which exists at and across the boundaries between disciplines
4. Support Communities of Practice (CoP) for Heliophysics that provide new linkages and produce capable processes and technologies to utilize the knowledge and thus enhance knowledge transfer and innovation in every discipline
5. Actively support diversity, equity, and inclusion and support underrepresented members of our community (i.e., embrace plurality of thought)

References

- [1] National Research Council. *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*.